

A picking strategy for omnidirectional mobile robots

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Abstract—Strategies for picking ”on-the-fly” play an important role in modern production systems since they can reduce lead time. This paper presents a path planning technique for pick-on-the-fly strategies with mobile robots, which is based on conveyor tracking approaches. Experimental tests were carried out to validate the proposed strategy.

Index Terms—mobile robot, picking, path-planning

I. INTRODUCTION

To make production processes more efficient, companies have been adopting robots capable of interacting with moving objects in order to pick and manipulate them without stopping the production process, thus reducing the cycle time. This is usually achieved by tracking moving objects, usually placed on conveyor belts (conveyor tracking strategy). The interaction of robots with moving objects usually is based on three elements [2]:

- a *vision system* to locate the object at a certain time instant;
- a *conveyor belt* that provides the motion of the object and by means of its sensors provides the position of the object placing on it to the robot;
- a *robot manipulator* to grasp the object.

Despite the literature having provided solutions for visual or conveyor tracking in the past [3], [4], there has been limited work on picking ”on-the-fly” strategies for mobile robots, which are becoming more common in industrial environments.

The novelty of this work is the implementation of conveyor tracking techniques to mobile robots. Indeed, to the authors’ knowledge, the literature focuses on presenting path-planning for squads of mobile robots to substitute conveyors [1] or to pick an object through visual tracking techniques with the mobile platform stopping near the target [5], with the stop increasing the cycle time.

II. PICKING STRATEGY

For the picking strategy to be effective, a suitable set of reference systems is required. With reference to Figure 1, four reference frames are considered: the mobile robot (M), the robot arm (R), the part (P), and the absolute (W) reference frames.

Considering a part placed on a fixed pallet, the part position \mathbf{o}_P is defined as constant with respect to the absolute reference frame and set offline. However, one or more conveyor belts can be considered, in which case \mathbf{o}_P will be time-variant and

Fig. 1. The system layout with the reference frames: (W) World, (M) mobile robot, (R) robot arm and (P) part

another reference frame (B) for the belt should be included in the system.

For the robot arm to pick the part, it is necessary to define the part position in the robot reference frame $\mathbf{o}_{P,R}$, similarly to the traditional conveyor tracking approach. The part position and orientation with respect to the robot reference frame are defined through the 4x4 transformation matrix $\mathbf{T}_{P,R}$:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} o_P \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix}_R = [\mathbf{T}_{P,R}] \begin{Bmatrix} o_P \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix}_P \quad (1)$$

This matrix is time variant, leading to a behaviour similar to the traditional conveyor tracking problem, where the part moves in the robot reference frame. $\mathbf{T}_{P,R}$ can be evaluated by decomposing it into two reference frames

$$\mathbf{T}_{P,R} = \mathbf{T}_{W,R} \mathbf{T}_{P,W} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{T}_{P,W}$ is the transformation matrix that describes the part reference frame with respect to the world one, which is known and defined as constant in the proposed system for simplicity, and $\mathbf{T}_{W,R}$ is the transformation matrix that describes the world reference frame with respect to the robot one, and which is the time-variant part. To evaluate this matrix, it is useful to consider its inverse $\mathbf{T}_{R,W}$ which describes the robot in the world reference frame and can be decomposed into two further transformation matrices $\mathbf{T}_{R,M}$ and $\mathbf{T}_{M,W}$:

$$\mathbf{T}_{R,W} = \mathbf{T}_{M,W} \mathbf{T}_{R,M} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{T}_{R,M}$ is known and constant and $\mathbf{T}_{M,W}$ is variable and depends on the mobile robot path.

Given the position and orientation of the part with respect to the robot, it is possible to define the picking strategy. The pick and place task for the proposed method consists in three main movements: a movement from the mobile platform to the pallet over the part to be picked, a proper movement for picking that compensates for the platform motion, and a movement to the platform to place the part.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm was tested on the KUKA KMR iiwa platform, a mobile robot composed of an omnidirectional mobile platform and a 7-DOF serial manipulator.

In the proposed setup the aforementioned transformation matrices are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{T}_{P,W} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 2300 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & -750 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 300 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{R,M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 417.2 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & -200 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_{M,W} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_M(t)) & -\sin(\theta_M(t)) & 0 & X_M(t) \\ \sin(\theta_M(t)) & \cos(\theta_M(t)) & 0 & Y_M(t) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The trajectory chosen for the mobile base was a linear motion along the x_w axis with constant velocity equal to 100 m/s.

Figures 2 and 3 show the path of the robot end-effector during the picking task adopting the traditional approach, i.e., stopping the mobile robot during the grasping task, and the proposed strategy, respectively.

Fig. 2. Path of the robot end-effector in the absolute reference frame with the traditional approach

The two trajectories in the absolute reference frame are mostly similar. However, it is possible to observe that the position of the placing point in Figure 3 is shifted along the x -axis due to the platform motion. The difference between the approaches is more visible considering the motion in the robot reference frame, where it is possible to observe that the picking motion of the robot (in the red circle) is not vertical

Fig. 3. Path of the robot end-effector in the absolute reference frame with the proposed approach

Fig. 4. Path of the robot end-effector in the robot reference frame with the proposed approach

but follows the platform motion. Several tests were carried out for different value of the mobile robot speed, showing a reduction in the picking task duration up to 45%.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a picking strategy for omnidirectional mobile robots to pick the parts "on-the-fly", thus reducing the lead time characteristic of these operations. Experimental tests were carried out and the strategy was compared with the traditional approach for different speeds of the mobile platform, showing a reduction in the cycle time.

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